

Reaction of Ethyl Diazoacetate with Aldehydes and Ketones

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Aldehydes¹, ordinary ketones², cyclic ketones³, and acid chlorides⁴, form an unstable dihydrooxadiazole with diazomethane. Nitrogen escapes and a proton, alkyl group or chloro atom, respectively rearranges⁵.

Similarly ethyl diazoacetate reacts with benzaldehyde to give ethyl benzoyl acetate⁶. In the present investigation the author extended this reaction using acetaldehyde, acetone and cyclopentanone to react with ethyl diazoacetate.

The interaction of ethyl diazoacetate with acetaldehyde, acetone and cyclopentanone in the presence of a catalytic amount of silver oxide yields products which lose nitrogen to give ketonic derivatives. The products isolated are colourless liquids which give 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives, identified by comparison of infrared spectra with an authentic sample and by analysis. Using different conditions by heating the reaction mixture for periods of 1 hr., 3 hr., or 6 hr. or using different proportions of the carbonyl compounds does not alter the yield.

The probable pathway proposed for these reactions involves the formation of unstable oxadiazole intermediate (I), which loses nitrogen, followed by rearrangement to give ketonic compounds (II), (III).

R = Alkyl, Phenyl group.

R' = Alkyl, Hydrogen atom.

R,R' = $-\text{CH}_2-(\text{CH}_2)_2-\text{CH}_2-$

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EXPERIMENTAL

Melting points are uncorrected. Analysis were carried out by Alfred Bernhardt, Max-Planck Institute, Mulheim, Ruhr, Germany. Infrared spectra were measured on a Perkin-Elmer Infracord Model 137E spectrophotometer.

Action of ethyl diazoacetate' on acetaldehyde: A mixture of acetaldehyde (0.1 *M*), ethyl diazoacetate (0.05 *M*) and silver oxide (0.1 g.) was placed in 150 ml. r.b. flask, fitted with a reflux condenser. The flask was heated in an oil bath at 130–140° for 6 hrs. The reaction mixture was fractionated under reduced pressure. The first fraction gave acetaldehyde. The fraction distilled at 160°/3 mm. gave ethyl acetoacetate (1.5 g., 11.5%), identified by comparison of infrared spectra with authentic sample of ethyl acetoacetate.

Action of ethyl diazoacetate on acetone: A mixture of acetone (0.1 *M*), ethyl diazoacetate (0.05 *M*) and silver oxide (0.1 g.) was heated in a similar way. The reaction mixture was fractionated under reduced pressure and the first fraction was identified as acetone. The fraction distilled at 130°/0.6 mm. gave Ethyl α -methylacetoacetate (0.6 g., 3.5%). (Found: C, 58.4; H, 8.2; Calc. for $C_7H_{12}O_3$; C, 58.3; H, 8.3%).

Action of ethyl diazoacetate on cyclopentanone: A mixture of cyclopentanone (0.1 *M*), ethyl diazoacetate (0.05 *M*) and silver oxide (0.1 g.) was heated and distilled in a similar way. The fraction distilled at 85°/1.5 mm., gave Ethyl-1-cyclohexanone-carboxylate (0.5 g., 3.0%). (Found: C, 63.2; H, 8.4; Calc. for $C_9H_{14}O_3$: C, 63.5; H, 8.2). Reaction with 2,4-dinitro phenylhydrazine and crystallisation from ethanol gave the hydrazone derivative in yellow crystals m.p. 138°–139°.

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